

The Importance of Vocabulary: An Evaluation in the Context of Teachers' Views and Practices

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Abstract

Words, which are the basic elements of understanding and understanding, have important functions in teaching the mother tongue, recognizing the social culture, and developing the emotions and thoughts of the individual. For this reason, it can be said that teaching vocabulary and a developed vocabulary have important effects on the social and individual development of the individual. The purpose of this research; to reveal the importance of vocabulary in the context of teacher views and practices. The research was designed according to action research, one of the qualitative research methods. The study group of the research consists of 15 Turkish teachers selected by simple random sampling method. Research data were collected with a semi-structured interview. The obtained data were analyzed by content analysis technique In the study, it was concluded that the teachers considered teaching vocabulary necessary and important. In addition, in the research, it was stated that vocabulary teaching is a multidimensional and complex process; It has been concluded that the experience and knowledge of teachers in vocabulary teaching are different from each other and therefore they use very different approaches and techniques in teaching vocabulary.

Keywords: Vocabulary, Vocabulary teaching, Turkish lesson, Turkish teaching

Sözcük Dağarcığının Önemi: Öğretmen Görüşleri ve Uygulamaları Bağlamında Bir Değerlendirme

Öz

Anlama ve anlaşmanın temel öğeleri olan sözcükler ana dili öğretiminde, toplumsal kültürü tanıma, bireyin duyu ve düşünce gelişiminde önemli işlevlere sahiptirler. Bu nedenle sözcük öğretiminin ve gelişmiş bir sözcük dağarcığının bireyin sosyal ve bireysel gelişimi üzerinde önemli etkileri olduğu söylenebilir. Bu araştırmanın amacı; öğretmen görüşleri ve uygulamaları bağlamında sözcük dağarcığının önemini ortaya koymaktır. Araştırma, nitel araştırma yöntemlerinden eylem araştırmasına göre desenlenmiştir. Araştırmanın çalışma grubunu, basit seçkisiz örnekleme yöntemiyle seçilen 15 Türkçe öğretmeni oluşturmaktadır. Araştırma verileri yapılandırılmış görüşme formuyla toplanmıştır. Elde edilen veriler içerik analizi tekniğiyle analiz edilmiştir. Araştırmada öğretmenlerin sözcük öğretimini gerekli ve önemli gördükleri sonucuna ulaşılmıştır. Ayrıca araştırmada sözcük öğretiminin çok boyutlu ve karmaşık bir süreç olduğu; sözcük öğretimi konusunda öğretmenlerin deneyim ve bilgi birikimlerinin birbirinden farklı olduğu ve bu nedenle sözcük öğretiminde çok farklı yaklaşım ve teknikleri kullandıkları sonucuna ulaşılmıştır.

Anahtar Sözcükler: Sözcük bilgisi, Sözcük öğretimi, Sözcük dağarcığı, Türkçe dersi, Türkçe öğretimi

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Introduction

Humans have to communicate by nature. Communication between people can be written, verbal or visual. When people express themselves verbally or in writing, they do so in proportion to the vocabulary they know. The more vocabulary a person has, the easier it is to express himself. Especially in educational environments, students' vocabulary is of great importance. Because the students' understanding and expression is again in proportion to the words they know (Aykac, 2016). In order to raise individuals who question, criticize, discuss, produce conclusive solutions and gain high-level thinking skills, significant attention should be paid to the education of fluent reading skills (Tas & Zorba, 2022).

Words include the pronunciation features of a language, its sound syntactic structure; of nations they are voice associations that carry their knowledge, culture and experience. Linguistically when evaluated, it has a grammatical appearance and socio-cultural cultural units. In this respect, words describing the structure of a language in addition to being units, they reflect the memories and experiences of nations must see as. The vocabulary of language is the expression of human thoughts and feelings a society that has preserved its value as the existence of social interaction that has emerged from its depth has essence. Hearing the values and feelings of that language while people are learning their mother tongue, they want to feel and live (Karaduz, 2004).

Vendryes (2002) uses words as a sound to express concepts define them as unions. Therefore, vocabulary teaching is important in terms of language teaching it has a very special place. According to Vardar (2007) one or more sounds it is a semantic often formed by the unit, located between two spaces in the text. Various syntactic units that form a unit, present a certain formal unity in the discourse, either unchanged in form in their use or a form as in bents. Therefore, it can be said that the effective use of internal and external motivation tools by parents and teachers will increase the desire and frequency of reading in students, and will turn reading into a habit (Tas, 2018).

It is an articulated sound or group of sounds that changes with words are formed when sound units gain meaning in the mind. Words in this respect, they are units that have both sound and meaning images. When transcribed appear as written symbols. In this respect, sound in teaching words, concepts such as meaning and writing are taken into account. Teaching based on these concepts effective learning is achieved by using these techniques in vocabulary teaching. Words are the representations of intellectual or symbolic entities and concepts as sound and writing is the equivalent. While humans store intangible or tangible entities and concepts in their memory, always uses corresponding symbols (Karatay, 2007). Word definitions that lead to differentiation in the studies of it varies according to the way people approach the word concept. Some of them are based on the shape as the determining element in their definitions, some on the meaning, however, some try to bring together form and meaning (Kurudayioglu, 2005).

In the process of learning the native language, people hear these sound associations of their mother tongue tries to understand entities, facts and events. Consisting of sound and meaning words process the mental world of the individual from a young age. Each individual's mother tongue understands the outside world with words formed by combining their sounds and tells. One side of the words are sounds and the other side is concepts. Both sounds as well

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as concepts, the common utterance and expression of all members of the society. It is the product of your habits. Mental joint efforts of individuals in society and together while their utterances enable social thought to turn into voices, existence occurs. From the moment of birth, people encounter and are ready around them. the words he finds, the concepts that these words evoke, the words formed by the words stereotyped expressions create vocabulary. vital for the individual and society. The studies on creating the vocabulary of the language at different levels, which are important society for both directing the education and training of the individual and for sociological development. It is very important in terms of contributing to its shaping (Karaduz & Yildirim, 2011).

The word is an indication of the thoughts and attitudes we want to express. Akyol and Kirkkilic (2014), defines the word as the memory-stored form of experiences. Aksan (2000), the sign, which we call a word, is a concept and a sound aspect of every language. It is a fused thought-sound combination, a meaning and a meaning related to other elements in the language. Kantemir (1997), stated that the word is the unit of expression, the meaning of the word and the sentence. It defines it as a voice or a voice ensemble that plays an active role in the establishment. Korkmaz (2008), people who speak the same language, consisting of one or more phonemes. When used alone in the mind, the concrete or abstract or concrete and abstract concepts that reflect a certain feeling or thought language unit that establishes a relationship between. According to this definition, the word it is both a meaning and a shape unit. A close relationship between word and concept available. When the word is said, the concept that corresponds to it comes to mind. Their formation for feelings, thoughts, dreams, etc. having imagination in memory and expressing it it should be a word (Alperen, 2001).

The individual's ability to express himself and the people he communicates with vocabulary knowledge is very important for understanding. A person wins all words are called vocabulary. Korkmaz (2008) vocabulary; your language all the words; words in the vocabulary of a person or a community total defines as. When the studies are examined, these concepts expressed, it can be said that it is used to meet the same meaning among these concepts in. Aksan (2000), in which the meaning of "vocabulary" differs from the others, vocabulary, besides basic or core words; words of foreign origin, idioms, proverbs, terms consisting of concepts belonging to science, art and technical fields and patterns made up of words. The basic vocabulary, also called basic words, seen in the oldest texts remaining from the ancestors and is of primary importance to man counted items. These are the names of organs, food and drink, agricultural tools, people names of closely related animals, kinship names and numbers indicating are words with the definition (Ozbay & Melanlioglu, 2008).

Words, hearing, thinking, perceiving, learning, comparing, meanings it is used as a tool in the realization of many mental processes such as creating. While the individual acquires the concepts of the mother tongue at every age, the concepts of the mother tongue. Through it, he feels the pleasure of the culture he lives in. In this respect, at any age, in every period vocabulary teaching gains importance in the educational process. From the first year of primary school beginning from the beginning, purposeful and systematic vocabulary teaching studies should be carried out and students' vocabulary should be enriched. Your teachers especially with the vocabulary teaching activities that they take by taking their time not only add to their vocabulary the words processed by those activities, but also at the same time, vocabulary learning, meaning construction, mind and thought development, vocabulary understands the

importance of using newly added words orally and in writing, internalize it (Gocer, 2009). Meaningful form of language made up of sounds units are important in the process of hearing, thinking, and communicating strongly to the society provides advantages. Thanks to the vocabulary that the individual has, the society in which he lives recognizes the material and spiritual culture, becomes familiar with this culture. Words enriching our thoughts, the development of our material and spiritual culture provides. The deficiency in the vocabulary is the individual's ability to ignore any thought to understand; describe the situation he feels or tries to make sense of there is a blocking problem. Words are used in the formation and acquisition of concepts. They are symbols, and they also play an important role in mental development. This In this respect, vocabulary acquisition is of great importance for people in terms of language development (Yaman & Gulcan, 2009).

Vocabulary is the accumulation stored in memory as a result of an individual's learning experience means. It will enable to increase and use this accumulation in the most efficient way the environment is Turkish course. In this course, with the activities to enrich the vocabulary. It is ensured that the student both uses the language well and develops the world of thought (Diliduzgun, 2014). The words that we encounter and find ready around us from the moment we are born, the concepts and stereotypes evoked by these words form our vocabulary. Vocabulary is very important both for directing the education and training of the individual and for his sociological development.

At every stage of education, there is a need for sufficient vocabulary acquisition for active learning to take place. Therefore, one of the basic principles applied during mother tongue teaching is to improve the vocabulary of the target audience. A sufficiently developed vocabulary is an indispensable condition for comprehension and expression skills. Vocabulary proficiency is important not only in comprehension and expression studies, but also in other areas. It is not possible to say that there is a special program to improve vocabulary in our country (Vendryes, 2002). The fact that our students who start higher education do not have sufficient vocabulary and cause them to fall short of expressing themselves must be the result of this indifference. However, a student who has completed secondary education should have the ability to use their mother tongue perfect.

Textbooks used in the education and training process are indispensable elements of the education system. Especially Turkish textbooks are of vital importance in this regard. Because the books in which the rules of our mother tongue Turkish are taught and the words that the student will use throughout his life are taught are Turkish textbooks. From this point of view, the vocabulary of Turkish textbooks is very important. Because vocabulary, if not the only factor in determining the richness of the language, is one of the most important factors. It can also be mentioned that the vocabulary has a positive effect on school life, social life and working life. Because the individual with a rich vocabulary will understand the sources they read and listen to more easily. The world of thought of a person who expresses his feelings and thoughts with words can be rich in proportion to his vocabulary (Kurudayioglu, 2005).

Vocabulary, which has an important place in the acquisition of basic skills in Turkish lessons, makes it easier for students to understand and explain what they read and listen to correctly (Sever, 2011). In this case, the lack of vocabulary may cause the person to not express himself/herself sufficiently and not to understand what is expressed sufficiently. Language is shaped by the formation of the vocabulary, and the words that people add to their vocabulary

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mean accumulation for the language they speak (Tosunoglu, 1999). The more this accumulation, the greater the ability to use the language. Individuals with low vocabulary often speak and write the same words. In this case, these people have to express their feelings and thoughts with a limited number of words. However, individuals with a rich vocabulary are able to convey their feelings and thoughts with more words and more easily (Baldan, 2009).

Achievement in basic language skills such as reading, writing, listening and speaking vocabulary plays a huge role. According to Akyol and Kirkkilic (2014), the word treasury has positive effects on success in reading. Word there are two types of words in our vocabulary, active and passive. Written and oral the words that we can use comfortably and easily in the expression are active, and the words we understand when we encounter them in a text are passive. The words we know are more than the words we use; active word used, the passive word is known (Aslan, 2017)

Words are the language that supports the individual's all kinds of learning and development. They are meaningful units made up of sounds. In these units, the sounds have a certain syntax forms words with rules. This points to the verbal side of the words it does. In the process of acquiring the individual's mother tongue, the pronunciation of sound units with meaning gains some emotional and cognitive gains while learning. This the gains are in the individuals' world of thought and emotion, in their personality, in their knowledge appear as values. All these values are important in every learning of the individual. It creates infrastructure and support for it. The relationship between vocabulary and school success a lot of research has been done on the it turns out that there is a relationship. Today, a lot of research on word recognition and establishes a direct link between mental dictionary and school success. In researches, it has been determined that students whose mental dictionaries are rich and that their school success as well as thinking, understanding, questioning, associating, classifying, sequencing, etc. Mental the skills turned out to be high (Gunes, 2007).

At school, the concept world is loaded with information in many fields to individuals trying to be enriched. In this context, teaching vocabulary in Turkish lessons the child has a special place in terms of conceptual development. Vocabulary width is also important in terms of the social and emotional development of the child. Child in order to be effective in society, one must be able to get along with others. child's Word the poverty of his repertoire can exclude him from society. Boy say something dream when he wants to but cannot explain his problem due to lack of words will be disappointed (Calp & Calp, 2016).

In this study, students' vocabulary in Turkish course in primary schools was investigated how the applications for the development of the treasury are carried out. Teachers' opinions about students in Turkish lessons the quality of the textbooks for the realization of the vocabulary, knowledge and experience and the applications made accordingly are very important. In this respect, how teachers carry out vocabulary studies in the research, how they found the textbooks, with which methods and techniques they applied their applications enrichment is under investigation.

Method

Research Model

This research is based on action research, one of the qualitative research methods patterned. Action research examines a situation, event and phenomenon in one's own life. It is based on presenting within the framework (Yildirim & Simsek, 2021). Data for research the interview technique was used to collect.

Study Group

Since qualitative methods were used in this study, it was randomly selected in the study. It is the method in which the selected units are taken into the sample by giving equal probability of being selected to each sample selection (with or without the selected unit being replaced). In this sampling method, all units in the universe have an equal and independent chance to be selected for the sample (Buyukozturk, Akgun, Karadeniz, Demirel & Kilic, 2021). Scientific research methods. Ankara: Pegem AcademyA study group of 15 people was formed. Identified working group or the sample was chosen from Turkish teachers working in Ordu. The teachers who participated in the group teachers meeting held throughout the province in the sample among 15 Turkish teachers within the framework of this research has been discussed. Seven of these teachers are male and eight are female teachers. The teachers in the sample have experience in different professional years. Before the interview, an appointment was made with the teachers, and then in a suitable environment interviews were held.

Data Collection

In the study, the data were collected with a semi-structured interview form prepared by the researcher. Semi-structured interview forms consist of certain questions and the participants reveal their personal views and thoughts with their answers to the questions (Yildirim & Simsek, 2021). The opinions of two field experts were taken for the questions in the interview form. With the prepared semi-structured interview form, we first met with 3 teachers. A pilot application was carried out. Interview based on pilot application data Necessary changes were made to the form. In the context of teacher opinions based on the emerging concepts, the questions were rearranged before 4 the number of questions was increased to 15. In this case, the questions used in the research important to support its validity. Therefore, within the scope of the research the number of questions has been increased in order to determine the points to be discussed. It is aimed to reach in a shorter time. However, at the end of the meeting, it is possible to obtain as much data as possible from the interviews, where different views were also included. It has been tried to pass for a long time. Sufficient time has been devoted to negotiations, the teachers answered the questions sincerely.

In this research, the principles of scientific research and publication ethics were followed. For this study, the approval of the Ethics Committee dated 25.03.2023 and numbered 63 was obtained from Ordu University.

Analysis of Data

The collected data is analyzed by content analysis coded and evaluated. Content analysis; it is an analysis technique that brings together similar data around certain categories and themes in

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an understandable way and allows to make inferences (Yildirim & Simsek, 2021). In content analysis, it is the conceptualization of the investigated event or phenomena, and the bringing together of similar ones. Similar concepts expressed in this way are brought together and categorized. It is possible to talk about an inductive process here (Ozdemir, 2018). After the opinions of the interviewed teachers were obtained in writing, each the teacher's written statement was coded. Based on the coding, categories and sub-categories were reached. Subcategories and categories are expressed as titles and subtitles in the findings section. For example, the "perspectives" of the teachers, the sub-title of "word teaching" "necessity" was considered as a sub-category.

Findings

1. Perspectives

a. Necessity of Vocabulary Teaching:

All of the interviewed teachers believed that vocabulary teaching was necessary. have expressed their opinion. "Why is it necessary?" different in question they have approaches. Five of the teachers were concerned about the effect of words on "understanding" while six teachers talked about its effect on "expressing".

For example:

"People think only as much as they know. We have to learn all the words, old or new. Not learning old words weakens our understanding. Students do not understand old texts." (T3)

"Learning vocabulary is absolutely essential. Because the child cannot understand the text without knowing the word." (T5)

"Vocabulary is necessary for students to better understand texts. Otherwise texts remain abstract and students cannot fully understand." (T6)

Here are the codes included in the comprehension category. Some teachers of understanding are dependent on understanding and past texts. thus interpreting it as a continuation; some teachers use the textual meaning and Turkish talks about the objectives of the lesson.

For example:

"Vocabulary should be rich for expression skill. Vocabulary development, child's ability to express himself extremely important." (T9)

"A person whose vocabulary is not rich cannot speak, cannot express herself comfortably." (T15)

Three teachers considered the subject as a duty, a necessity for the Turkish lesson has received.

For example:

"It should be stopped because one of the objectives of the Turkish lesson is the child's vocabulary develop his treasury." (T4)

"Vocabulary should be enriched. Because that's the teacher's job anyway." (T2)

According to these thoughts, it is necessary for students to develop and express themselves vocabulary needs to be developed. In these two approaches, there is basically the following difference, the former ones are the recipients or while emphasizing the importance of passive words, the latter are expressive, that is, active. They focus on the necessity of words. In fact, these thoughts all must be taken into account in the learning and teaching process. Students learning to develop both receptive and expressive words status should be included.

b. Adequacy of Textbooks

At this stage, the words in the teachers' reading passages level and the adequacy of the activities in the workbooks opinions were received. Five of the teachers learned that the words in the reading passages expressed his opinion that he did not find it appropriate for his level. If the reason for this that children do not understand the words and that some words in the texts are not in the dictionaries explained as their absence.

For example:

"Student use of the words in the reading passages not appropriate for the level. There are very old words that are not used today." (T3)

"Student use of the words in the reading passages not appropriate for the level. There are even words in the texts that are not in the dictionaries. Also, the texts are too long to understand." (T2)

"Student use of the words in the reading passages. I can't say it's appropriate. Some texts are too heavy for even teachers to understand." (T5)

"The words in the reading texts are definitely not appropriate for your level. The Ministry needs to find a solution to this immediately. It is very difficult to explain the terms in the theme of science and technology to village children." (T7)

Three of the teachers said that the words in the reading texts were at the level of the students, indicated that they were suitable.

For example:

"To level the words in the reading texts to the student level. I find it appropriate. I think there is no problem." (T3)

"The level of the words in the reading texts I think it is appropriate. Since the texts were prepared by experts, this detail was considered." (T6)

Four of the teachers said that the publishing houses of the books were different, the class taking into account variables such as the change of parts according to the level of they did not generalize.

For example:

"It depends on the grade level. Some of the texts in 7th grade heavy. There is no problem with the 8th grade texts." (T7)

"I cannot generalize for all books. Because the situation varies according to the publisher." (T9)

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On the adequacy of the activities in the workbooks five of the teachers expressed positive opinions visualization and application. They said that the activities based on the subject attracted the attention of the children and therefore they found the activities instructive.

For Example:

“Exercise activities of giving four or five words and writing text out of them are helpful. I find it.” (T3)

“Actually, the activities in the workbooks make words better and more effective very good for learning. Students are doing interesting and entertaining work with pleasure.” (T11)

“I think it is enough if applied properly. In particular, forecasting and that puzzle solving activities are more effective on students, I'm observing.” (T12)

“The events are better and more colorful than the old program formerly words sentence was given. Now there are activities such as matching and puzzles. I am satisfied.”(Interviewer 3)

“Sufficient. Of course, they come across more words, but those in the event it's good for us that they even learn how much.” (T15)

Eight teachers who found the activities insufficient since the number of words is low, it is very important to find out the meaning relations between the words. They complain that the students are not doing the activities unconsciously because they are not focused on.

For example:

“I don't think the events are enough. Not much on metaphorical meaning, synonym, antonym does not stop. In the past, there was more activity on this subject.” (T5)

“Events are not enough. Events are not permanent. Reading habit should be gained.” (T9)

“Events are, in my opinion, a tinted version of the past. Students activities only he does it because the teacher wants it.” (T10)

“Not enough, because more than what is covered at events unknown word. Then I underline and give homework. Sometimes in class we are talking.” (T14)

Two of the teachers interviewed were teaching old vocabulary. They expressed their opinion that their methods were more effective.

For example:

“I think our vocabulary is good, it means we learned more words in time. I think the old way is better.” (T2)

“Contemporary method techniques in vocabulary teaching, besides, classical methods should also be used.” (T13)

2. Applications

Teachers who agree on the necessity of teaching vocabulary opinions on the adequacy of textbooks differ. In this situation teachers' practices for teaching vocabulary gain importance. The opinions of the teachers on this subject are within the framework of the following sub-headings we can sum up:

a. Dictionary use: All of the teachers use the dictionary deemed necessary for teaching. Students' every lesson dictionary, spelling guide and teachers who want them to have a dictionary of proverbs and idioms with them are in the majority.

For example:

“Students should have both vocabulary and a dictionary of proverbs and idioms with them. Children are also they should understand that it is necessary for the Turkish lesson.” (T1)

“I require the use of a dictionary. Especially during reading hours, I want other friends to find words from the dictionary without distracting them.” (T10)

“Having a dictionary is mandatory in my class. Because they don't know or guess when there is a word they cannot understand, it is important for learning that they find it themselves without having to say it.” (T12)

In addition to the three teachers who do not make it compulsory to bring a dictionary, it is mandatory. However, those who do not control very tightly and consider it sufficient to have a few people in the class there are also teachers.

For example:

“Both vocabulary and proverbs and idioms from my students. I want them to bring the dictionary. However, I cannot say that all students bring every lesson. A dictionary is usually accompanied by five or six students. is happening. They find the meaning of the word and read it in class.” (T2)

“I made the dictionary mandatory, but I don't think too many of my students brought it. I have a few students who bring it all the time, and they find the word and read it in class.” (T3)

Those who agree on using a dictionary during the lesson our teachers first guess the meaning of the word from the context of the text and then refer to the dictionary.

For example:

“First I try to guess the meaning of the word. Children usually find the right answer anyway.”(T5)

“We do the activities during the lesson. Especially when reading texts I ask students to underline words they do not know. Unknown I have the paragraph in which the word is read, but my students are guessing they are struggling. I can say that this is because they do not read books.” (T7)

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b. Proverbs and Idioms:

All of the teachers expressed their opinions about the teaching of proverbs and idioms. However, the students understand the idioms. Teachers, who stated that they have difficulties, can use technology in today's conditions. They emphasized that it is caused by being dependent, lack of communication with adults and reading less books.

For example:

“Children find the meanings of the words but cannot guess the idioms. Children cannot distinguish between idioms and proverbs.” (T4)

“Students have a hard time finding the meaning of idioms, reading habit students with a skepticism can guess, but others have a hard time on idioms. I think that the social environment is also effective.” (T6)

In the teaching of idioms, every week or every lesson is an idiom to dwell on, to tell the origin stories of idioms, to play with drama or play to guess the meaning of the idiom, such as using it in their own speech methods appear to have been used.

For example:

“The proverbs I asked in compositions when I see that they do not understand, I do not dwell on proverbs and idioms any longer. I came to the conclusion that it is necessary” (T8)

“Proverbs and idioms are something that we can tell by making longer sentences. They are practical expressions that help us briefly describe the situation, the event. That's why I too ear familiarity with them, using them frequently as their teachers. I am trying to create.” (T10)

“I often dwell on proverbs and idioms. Because these I think it enriches students' ability to interpret. This with drama or a story, guessing the idiom or proverb I often use the tell your friends contest. So having fun I observe what they learn.” (T12)

“I share the origin stories of idioms and proverbs with students. This ensures permanence.” (T13)

“I dwell on proverbs and idioms every lesson. Each lesson is different I want them to say and investigate. Sometimes students are from their own families. They share the idioms they hear in the class.” (T15)

c. Use of Turkish Words

All of the interviewed teachers are foreigners who settled in our language thinks that Turkish should be used instead of words. In order to achieve this, such as giving performance homework and hanging posters on the boards indicate that they use methods.

For example:

“Students use the word "pardon" a lot. I say this is wrong.” (T4)

d. Using Additional Study and Materials

The vast majority of teachers state that they work outside of the activities in the book. We can group the work done as follows.

Practical activities: Four teachers, newly learned the use of words in speaking and writing advocates.

For example:

“By doing debating and speaking activities, they learn new words, I want them to use proverbs and idioms here.” (T2)

Activities for remembering: Five teachers expresses that the words should be repeated as often as possible in the lessons.

For example:

“I created a word box. Put the words we learned into that box. we throw if the lesson ends early, we draw words from that box and work on it.” (T3)

Current methods: working papers, concept maps, visuals five teachers explained how to use and benefit from associations advocates.

For example:

“Various word games, concept maps, association maps, word wall, sentence completion, making use of semantic links, etc. I include events from time to time.” (T8)

Creating a dictionary: Renew some of the students' notebooks. two teachers explained the idea of separating them into the words they learned advocates.

For example:

“The words we just learned are like a dictionary behind the notebook I'm printing.” (T1)

Playing games: Two teachers try to derive words that measure vocabulary based competitions are necessary.

For example:

“I have a word generation contest once a week. Students from this she enjoys it a lot.” (T5)

“Occasionally I play games like the One Word One trading contest. I see that students are very enthusiastic, but I don't always have time.” (T7)

3. Challenges Encountered

Teachers describe the difficulties they encounter while teaching vocabulary in different fields they have associated. We can list these areas as follows:

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a. Student difficulties

Five teachers emphasize that students should not repeat what has been learned.

For example:

“After doing word work to prevent forgetfulness and correct pronunciation, two I get it to work again the next day.” (T12)

“Because they don't repeat the words they just learned they forget.” (T5)

Three teachers emphasized that students do not have a habit of reading books is doing.

For example:

“Reading books is of great importance on learning words reading I'm trying to create the request. We are making progress thanks to reading hours. We should create a love, effort and desire to read books not only at school, but everywhere.” (T9)

“As a nation, we have the disease of not reading books. students again when we do not learn and do not read books, what we teach is not effective.” (T8)

Three teachers emphasize the reluctance of the students.

For example:

“Students are reluctant to do activities and mix dictionaries. I try to gamify, but since the course is in Turkish, I cannot concretize everything.” (T3)

b. Difficulties arising from the structure of the word

Two teachers expressed the difficulties caused by the abstractness of the words is doing.

For example:

“The words used in some texts are very heavy. The child does not understand the text, the text remains abstract.” (T6)

One teacher states that it is not used in daily life.

For example:

“Students cannot learn words that they do not use in their daily lives. It cannot be learned even if the teacher tells or repeats it.” (T2)

c. Environmental challenges

Two teachers expressed opinions about environmental factors.

For example:

“Since the place where I work is a small place, the children already have few words from their surroundings they hear. Also, families cannot gain the habit of reading books.” (T4)

d. Difficulties due to lack of resources

Three teachers voiced the problem of insufficient resources related to vocabulary teaching.

For example:

“There is no dictionary that shows examples of using idioms. I think that such a study for idioms should be done.” (T7)

“The resources to be used in language teaching are very limited. The existing ones are also prepared for commercial purposes. Not functional resources.” (T11)

Discussion, Conclusion and Recommendations

Discussion and Conclusion

Words, which are the basic building blocks of language, are used in understanding and understanding are the lexical meaningful morphemes used. Teachers written and oral teaching the lexical morphemes of the language, which is the main tool of expression, agree on its necessity. Some of the teachers' words while evaluating it as a basic element in creating meaning, some considers it as the main element in the narrative. Students' formal understand the text correctly and express themselves in the learning process are the reasons put forward for the development of vocabulary. According to Cecen (2007), a student's constant vocabulary development makes him successful in reading, writing and communicating. According to Bozdemir (2020), a student with a poor vocabulary has difficulty writing down thoughts and feelings; always set your mind since he writes with words, he cannot save himself from cliché words. Word a student whose treasury is rich; lecture in life as well as in school ease, the ability to understand what he reads easily and correctly. Vocabulary essential for success in reading, writing and speaking deems necessary.

Because of these concerns, teachers also stated that it is necessary to develop the vocabulary. Teachers differ in the methods and purposes of vocabulary teaching practices and approaches. A great deal of teachers part of the problem will be solved by teaching the meaning of the words. The pronunciation of words is hardly taken into account. to Cecen (2007) stated that both the spelling and pronunciation of a word are correct must be taught. Speech is important for communication.

Developing vocabulary in textbooks and dictionaries very important in terms of variety of words in textbooks, level, techniques used in teaching, which teachers focus on are concepts. Besides the textbooks, the dictionaries used by the students the quality is also very important. One of the main functions of dictionaries is to their duties in learning and teaching lots of words the rich conceptual world of the language is presented to the individuals by including the meaningfulness in the dictionaries. It helps individuals who learn their mother tongue to think correctly and information is supported. How to express polysemy in dictionaries In this regard, it is also important to know which narrative methods and techniques are used is important. The abundance of knowledge in learning does not mean anything by itself. The learners make sense of this information, and the teachers express the knowledge. The correctness and sufficiency of the methods and techniques used in considered sufficient to complete the learning (Karaduz, 2009).

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Since each word will be taught in a certain age period, this is in the textbooks. situation must be taken into account. According to Ari, Okur and Yilmazer (2010) word education begins at an early age in children and continues until youth with each learned word, the child's vocabulary is enriched. vocabulary learning it continues in the advanced ages, which we call the maturity age of the human, but childhood and not as fast as the youth period. A person has a great deal of knowledge with the words he has acquired. He earns his part in childhood and youth. Teachers have an opinion they are not united. The words are suitable for the level of the students. Teachers who say that they are not the teachers in the group stated that the words were above the level of the students they complain about it. However, in the preparation of textbooks the words students need are leveled through the texts should also be presented to the students. Ari, Okur and Yilmazer (2010) states that children are gradually taught vocabulary in texts abroad. One of the points to be considered while developing it is unnecessary to teach unused words to students specifies. The words used by the teachers in this group it was seen that he did not insist on teaching the other teachers any criticism while saying there is no problem with they avoid. Activities from textbooks there are different opinions among teachers about the issue.

Activities, games, colorfulness in the textbooks between words, with teachers saying that they motivate students. Learning on the basis of meaning that there are no meaning relations teachers who say they lack the techniques to perform has. In this regard, students scribble the activities aimlessly, they cannot achieve permanent learning. Between two groups of teachers there are fundamental differences of opinion. Satisfied with textbooks teachers evaluate textbooks formally. The formal aspect of textbooks is important for them in learning. Other teachers, on the other hand, use meaning and function in vocabulary development studies they give more importance and therefore they bring criticism. Teachers who criticize the meaning, especially the polysemy since there is no need for metaphor and connotation concepts in the textbooks, they mention that there is no place. Indeed the vocabulary polysemy is very important in their work. According to Saussur it has meanings that occur in the text, not dictionary meanings. (Aksan, 2000).

Each word gains meaning according to the context and vocabulary polysemy was taught to students based on the text from their studies should be perceived. According to Cetinkaya (2005), students learn with words they have just learned different sentences in which the same word occurs so that they can form related sentences become aware of how to use them in a context by giving patterns required. This is done through practice, not through dry repetitions should be provided. When teaching words, not only the meaning of the word in the text, but also all its meanings should be emphasized as much as possible. Your words suddenly more meanings should be taught and the opportunity to use them should be provided. The text of the Word repetition and exercises by associating the meanings outside the text with their meanings in the text must be taught through.

Teachers participating in the research use proverbs and words in vocabulary teaching idiom studies, using pure Turkish words, creating a dictionary, very little however, they use techniques such as concept maps and puzzles. This activities such as these will enable the student to make mental repetitions are learning processes. Vocabulary teaching multiple and interactive learning processes as it is a complex and difficult process must create (Ari, Okur & Yilmazer, 2010). All of the methods teachers use in teaching vocabulary It is one of the methods

recommended in the literature. However, in these applications as there is no unity among teachers, teachers are individually there are also no systematic applications developed. Conscious, systematic, holistic the chosen method is correct because it is not applied with an approach is not sufficient for teaching (Karaduz & Yildirim, 2011).

In the study, teachers' willingness to teach vocabulary they have chosen the right methods, but they are unplanned and unplanned about the application. We can conclude that they are unconscious. However, the reason for this is only it would be unfair to blame it on teachers. Cecen (2007) word the most important of the problems related to the treasury is that Turkish should be taught the fact that the vocabulary has not been determined says in the education system. This shortcoming is naturally reflected in the practices of teachers.

One of the methods that teachers use incompletely is the dictionary to keep the notebook. In the practices of some of the teachers dictionary book is included. However, the application is a newly learned writing the dictionary meaning of the word and forming at most one example sentence is in the form. Ozbay and Melanlıoğlu (2008) creating a dictionary book and the use of it says: "The purpose here is only it should not be to write and learn the learned word and the meaning of the word, on the contrary the page is divided into two or three parts, with the word details, meaning, type and example must be learned by its use in a sentence. In this context, the subject and it can be said that it can be written and taught according to its linguistic functions."

In practice, most of the teachers stated that the dictionary should be used they have stopped. Taking the context as a basis when finding the meaning of words there are also teachers who argue that vocabulary studies pole initiating meaning from the textual context, not the dictionary and then to use the studies for lexical meaning require a process. Repeats the implied meaning of words it should be taught to students with games in a way that creates a permanent and enjoyable learning processes should be designed. As in the traditional education system students who are out of context can only use simple and short sentences their studies help them to enrich their vocabulary does not provide (Akarsu, 2010). Newly learned words some of the features are listed as follows (Cecen, 2007): It should be valuable and responsive to students' personal needs. It should have a purpose and have purposes for students' learning. It should be covered throughout the curriculum.

In the research, the teachers encountered while teaching vocabulary they did not address these points in the problems, they gave a holistic approach to vocabulary teaching. It was revealed that they did not develop a point of view. Questioning the curriculum and instead of addressing whether the words meet the need or not. It has been seen that they tend to teach the drawn frame in the best way.

Language is a language that has a grammatical aspect as well as a socio-cultural dimension is the case. The structure of the language, the level of difficulty, socio-cultural conditions manifests itself as a factor in teaching. Vocabulary studies students have difficulty in learning because of the structure of some words. Formal side of words, polysemy, pronunciation problems, significance and narrative difficulties are important barriers. words of individuals his treasure is dependent on informal education as well as formal education. Each reading with the socio-cultural characteristics of the concept development family of the

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individual it also depends on your habits. Half of the participants in vocabulary teaching. The main difficulties encountered are the social characteristics of their environment they have come.

Recommendations

Perhaps the most important reason why vocabulary is considered important is that vocabulary is seen as a measure of the richness of languages and that people do this through vocabulary while expressing their feelings and thoughts. The success of people in expressing themselves can also be attributed to the vocabulary.

It cannot be denied that vocabulary has an important place in education as well. For this reason, it is necessary for students to have a sufficient vocabulary in the education process. In our country, no numerical target has been set for the vocabulary of the person according to age and level in the education process. For this reason, while some students try to improve their vocabulary with their personal efforts, some students are limited to their studies at school. It is considered important to give a separate place to vocabulary in Turkish Language Curriculum in order to provide a balance between people who develop their vocabulary with factors such as family, social environment, personal effort and those who are limited to activities at school.

With this research, it has been seen that teachers' experiences and their own perspectives are very important in the learning and teaching processes. Teachers often have different opinions cause applications. However, these situations are related to group work can be remedied. Teachers' vocabulary studies with new program jointly share new ideas and multiple learning environments together enhancements; they need to employ a variety of techniques.

In addition to vocabulary activities, it is also important that the texts selected for Turkish textbooks are suitable for the level and interest of the student, and consist of words with a high frequency of use that can be used in daily life. In addition, attention should be paid to the use of unknown words in other texts. Because it takes a long time to learn new words. Words that are stored in short-term memory when first heard are quickly forgotten if they are not transferred to long-term memory.

Before starting the vocabulary teaching, according to the age and interest levels of the students. A needs analysis should be done. In the Turkish Language Curriculum, which words are used according to the grade levels methods should also be mentioned. Texts created with words suitable for the level in the prepared textbooks should take place. The words to be taught should be given in context. During vocabulary studies, the habit of using a dictionary is given to the student should be introduced. Various methods and techniques that will attract the attention of the student in vocabulary studies techniques should be used. While teaching words, spelling and pronunciation should also be emphasized.

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Ethical Declaration and Committee Approval

In this research, the principles of scientific research and publication ethics were followed. For this study, the approval of the Ethics Committee dated 25.03.2023 and numbered 63 was obtained from Ordu University.

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